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SO I HEAR YOU ARE AN EXPERT ON ONLINE TEACHING NOW? SHARING THOUGHTS, EXPERIENCES, AND VISIONS ON ONLINE TEACHING FROM THE NEW GLOBAL ONLINE TEACHING COMMUNITY

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ABSTRACT

It is strange writing this abstract with the thought of the COVID-19 crisis having hopefully past and us returning to our normal academic lives for the SEFI2020 annual conference. But the crisis will eventually pass, and with its passing new opportunities will arise – some even from unexpected impacts of the crisis itself. One such impact is that we now have a global online teaching community.

Almost every teacher in post-secondary education was thrust into the deep end with respect to online education at the beginning of the crisis. My biggest fear is that negative experiences and frustrations may emerge and set in people's minds, framing online as the kryptonite of effective education. However, there is hope. With virtually everyone having some experience with online teaching and learning, we are positioned to have a very informed and potentially effective dialogue about the future of online teaching in engineering education with a wide diversity of informed views. The SIG on Open and Online Education would like to facilitate this dialogue through a workshop to discuss online education and collect the thoughts, experiences, and visions of the SEFI community on the topic.

In this workshop, we will be breaking into smaller groups to discuss and reflect on our experiences with respect to different topics around online learning. We hope to engage online education veterans as well as those that may have only been recently exposed to the world of online. Below is a preliminary list of topics, but these are subject to change as individual people are contacted to lead the discussion of the small group. For each of the topics, three basic questions will be examined:

1. What have your experiences over the past half year taught you with respect to the subgroup topic?
2. What do you think could/should be done in the future to further the potential of the subgroup topic in the future?

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3. What do you see as a possible role for SEFI in furthering the subgroup topic?

Topics being considered for the subgroups in the workshop at the moment include:

- Assessment in an online world
- From hands-on project learning to virtual project learning
- Engagement and interaction in an online environment
- Best practices and tools